

Table 2. Segregation for reaction to 2 isolates (race 003) of *Pyricularia oryzae* in the F₂ populations between NILS.^a

Cultivar, line, or cross	Seedlings (no.)			Goodness of fit		
	Resistant	Susceptible	Total	$\chi^2(3:1)$	$\chi^2(15:1)$	Probability
Isolate IBOS 1-1-1						
Nipponbare (\pm)	0	9	9			
Kanto-IL 7 (<i>Pi-i</i>)	10	0	10			
NipponbareKanto-IL 7	146	53	199	0.2831		0.50 - 0.60
Nipponbare (\pm)	0	8	8			
Kanto-IL 8 (<i>Pi-z'</i>)	9	0	9			
NipponbareKanto-IL 8	148	42	190	0.8491		0.30 - 0.40
Nipponbare (\pm)	0	10	10			
Kanto-IL 5 (<i>Pi-z</i>)	10	0	10			
NipponbareKanto-IL 5	143	51	194	0.1718		0.60 - 0.70
Isolate IBOS 1-1-1						
Nipponbare (\pm)	0	39	39			
Kanto-IL 7 (<i>Pi-i</i>)	10	0	10			
Kato-IL 8 (<i>Pi-z'</i>)	9	0	9			
Kanto-IL 7/Kanto-IL 8	350	26	376	0.2837		0.50 - 0.60
Nipponbare (\pm)	0	41	41			
Kanto-IL 5 (<i>Pi-z</i>)	10	0	10			
Kanto-IL 7 (<i>Pi-i</i>)	10	0	10			
Kanto-IL 5/Kanto-IL 7	462	35	497	0.5324		0.40 - 0.50
Isolate Ken 54-20						
Nipponbare (\pm)	0	10	10			
Kanto-IL 7 (<i>Pi-i</i>)	10	0	10			
Kanto-IL 8 (<i>Pi-z'</i>)	10	0	10			
Kanto-IL 7/Kanto-IL 8	184	13	197	0.0409		0.80 - 0.90
Nipponbare (\pm)	0	10	10			
Kanto-IL 5 (<i>Pi-z</i>)	10	0	10			
Kanto-IL 7 (<i>Pi-i</i>)	10	0	10			
Kanto-IL 5/Kanto-IL 7	191	13	204	0.0052		0.90 - 0.95

^a Blast resistance gene for each line is in parentheses.

Disease reactions were scored about 7 d after inoculation.

Inoculated seedlings clearly segregated into resistant and susceptible classes. Each segregation of F₂ populations derived from crosses between three NILs and the recurrent parent gave a good fit to a 3 resistant: 1 susceptible ratio. This shows that each NIL has a single dominant gene for resistance to the isolate IBOS 1-1-1 (Table 2).

Each segregation of four F₂ populations derived from crosses between the NIL with *Pi-i* and the NILs with *Pi-z* or *Pi-z'* gave a good fit to a 15 resistant: 1 susceptible ratio. This indicates that two independent dominant genes conferred resistance to the isolates belonging to race 3 (Table 2). These segregation patterns indicate no linkage relationships between *Pi-i* and *Pi-z* loci.

Some workers previously used breeding lines with *Pi-z* derived from distantly related crosses and a Japanese cultivar with *Pi-i* genetic analyses. These different genetic backgrounds or modifier gene(s) may cause an excess of resistant segregants in the F₂ populations, suggesting linkage in the repulsion phase. The NILs provide excellent material for characterizing each gene and for further genetic and pathologic studies. □

Pest resistance—insects

Identification of a new Asian rice gall midge (GM) population in Bhandara District, Maharashtra, India, and highly resistant genotypes

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Four biotypes (I to IV) of the Asian rice GM *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason) (Diptera: Cecidomyiidae) from different rice areas of India have been identified and characterized. Earlier trials with limited differentials showed that the Sakoli GM was similar to that from north

coastal Andhra Pradesh (NCAP) (biotype IV). Many GM-resistant rice donors and cultures, however, were susceptible at Sakoli, an area where GM is endemic. We studied 36 donors and cultures with known reactions to the biotypes during 1990 and 1991 kharif (monsoons).

Reaction of differentials to Indian GM biotypes from different locations, 1990-91 kharif. ^a

Biotype	Location	Reaction of differentials									
		Eswara-korra	Orumun-dakan	CR308-408	CR309-268	PTB10	R296-120	CR157-212	Vellu-tha-cheera	CRS7-Kaka-MR 1523	Kakatiya
I	Warangal, Andhra Pradesh (AP)	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
II	Cuttack, Orissa	S	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	S
III	Ranchi, Bihar	R	-	-	R	R	R	R	R	R	S
IV	Srikakulam, North Coastal AP	S	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	R
V	Sakoli, Maharashtra	R	S	S	S	R	R	R	R	R	S

^aS = susceptible, R = resistant.

The seed originated from CRRRI's insect-resistant donor garden. It was selected over several years for GM resistance under high GM pressure in the field.

The entries were transplanted in early August in Cuttack and in late August in Sakoli to allow for peak GM infestation by the 50-60 d after planting. We adopted

cultural practices to favor high GM buildup, including close spacing (15 × 15 cm), continuous standing water of 2-5 cm, and frequent N application. Susceptible checks Jaya in Cuttack and TN1 in Sakoli were interspersed in the plots at the beginning, end, and after every 10 test entries to serve as indicators for GM buildup. Only plants completely free from infestation were rated resistant (R), while those showing any infestation rated susceptible (S).

TN1 had 100% GM-infested hills and 75-89% infested tillers (silvershoots). Jaya had 99-100% infested hills and 59-73% infested tillers.

Brown planthopper (BPH)-resistant varieties developed at Moncompu, Kerala

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The BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) has caused extensive damage to Asian rice crops. Although the pest was reported in Kerala during 1958 and 1962, the first severe outbreak occurred in 1973-74, damaging about 50,000 ha of rice. Grain yield loss was 10-70% and at times reached 100%.

Host plant resistance is the logical approach to BPH control.

Breeding programs for BPH-resistant varieties began in 1973 at RRS. BPH-

Damage ratings were consistent in both years at both centers. Entries S in Sakoli but R in Cuttack were ARC5158, ARC6221, RPW6-4 (S.S), Leaug 152, Shakti, Samalei, OB677, Orumundakan, CR294-548, CR3 17-166, CR319-644, CR315-621, CR318-548-7, CR410-3225, CR410-3225-2, CR308-408, CR309-268, ARC5984, Swimphul, CR394-6056, CR410-6018, and CR392-5085-2.

Entries R in both Sakoli and Cuttack were AC1224, MNP76, PTB10, Banglei, CR57-MR 1523, CR311-134, CR157-212, Aganni, Eswarakorra, Velluthacheera, NHTA 8, and T1477.

resistant donors such as PTB20, Kochuvithu, Karivennel, IR1539, PTB33, ARC6650, and IR1561, and modern varieties such as IR8, IR11, Triveni, and Jaya were used.

Promising selections were obtained from crosses IR8/PTB20, IR11/Kochuvithu, IR8/Karivennel, Trivenil IR1539, Jaya/PTB33, ARC6650/Jaya, and IR1561/PTB33. Eight varieties were released from them during 1978-90.

We studied the reaction of seedlings to the local BPH biotype using the bulk seedling test. Varieties were also screened in the field under heavy natural incidence. Resistance was scored using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*. Results are presented in the table. □

Plant characters and BPH score of selections bred for BPH resistance in Kerala, India.

Variety	Parentage	Plant height (cm)	Crop duration (d)	Panicles (no./hill)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Grain type ^a	Protein content (%)	Reaction to BPH ^b		Release (year)
								Lab	Field	
MO 4 (Bhadra)	IR8m/PTB20	81	120 ^c 135 ^d	20.0	5.5	SB	10.2	2.8	2.5	1978
MO 5 (Asha)	IR11/Kochuvithu	85	120	7.5	6.0	LB	9.4	2.6	2.5	1980
MO 6 (Pavizham)	IR8/Karivennel	90	120	7.5	6.0	SB	7.5	2.0	2.3	1982
MO 7 (Karthika)	Triveni/IR1539	90	110	7.5	6.5	LB	10.6	2.0	2.0	1985
MO 8 (Aruna)	Jaya/PTB33	90	110	12.0	6.5	MB	9.6	2.2	1.7	1990
MO 9 (Makam)	ARC6650/Jaya	85	110	12.0	6.5	SB	9.4	1.7	2.5	1990
MO 10 (Remya)	Jaya/PTB33	110	120	10.0	6.5	LB	10.9	2.3	2.6	1990
MO 11 (Kanakam)	IR1561/PTB33	110	125	8.0	7.0	MB	9.5	1.6	2.0	1990
TN1 (susceptible check)		75	105	12.0	—	MB	—	9.0	9.0	—
PTB33 (resistant check)		135	130	6.0	—	MB	—	2.7	2.3	—

^a Cooking quality of all selections was good. SB = short bold, LB = long bold, MB = medium bold. All test varieties have red kernels.

^b By the *Standard evaluation system for rice*. ^c Dry season. ^d Wet season.

Orumundakan and its derivatives CR308-408 and CR309-268 were R in NCAP but S in Sakoli, Eswarakorra was R in Sakoli but S in NCAP, and Velluthacheera was S in NCAP but R at Sakoli. Sakoli GM was also different from that in Ranchi (III). CR57-MR 1523 was R in Sakoli and S in Ranchi; Kakatiya was the opposite.

Eswarakorra was R at both locations. PTB10 and its derivatives R296-120 and CR157-212 were R at all locations. Sakoli GM populations should be treated as a distinct biotype based on these results. □

Pest resistance—other pests

Upland rice cultivars resistant to parasitic weed *Striga hermonthica*

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Striga spp. are parasitic weeds of maize, sorghum, millet, and upland rice in Africa. No single method exists for controlling striga effectively. The pink-colored *S. hermonthica* (Del.) Benth. has become a serious problem in upland rice in western Kenya. We studied whether rice cultivars differed in relative resistance to *S. hermonthica*.

Forty upland rice lines from various sources were evaluated for reaction to striga during the 1990 short-rains cropping season (Sep-Dec). We conducted the experiment in a farmer's field that had a history of striga incident at Mbita Point under rainfed upland conditions (900 mm rain/yr). The soil is a calcaro-vertic Fluvisol with pH 8.1 and 0.9% organic C; each 100-g sample has CEC 37.5 meq, 0.1 meq K, and 36 meq P. Rice was planted in rows, 30 cm apart in 3- × 5-m plots, with four replications.

Striga plants were uprooted from plots at 95 d after rice emergence, dried, and weighed. Rice entries IR38547-B-B-7-2-2, IR47255-B-B-5-4, IR47697-4-3-1, and IR49255-B-B-5-2 were striga-free